

Neutrosophic Φ -open sets and neutrosophic Φ -continuous functions

Suman Das¹, and Surapati Pramanik^{2,*}

¹Department of Mathematics, Tripura University, Agartala, 799022, Tripura, India.

Email: suman.mathematics@tripurauniv.in, sumandas18842@gmail.com

²Department of Mathematics, Nandalal Ghosh B. T. College, Narayanpur, 743126, West Bengal, India.

Email: sura_pati@yahoo.co.in

* Correspondence: sura_pati@yahoo.co.in Tel.: (+91-9477035544)

Abstract: We introduce the notion of neutrosophic Φ -open set and neutrosophic Φ -continuous mapping via neutrosophic topological spaces and investigate several properties of it. By defining neutrosophic Φ -open set, neutrosophic Φ -continuous mapping, and neutrosophic Φ -open mapping, we prove some remarks, theorems on neutrosophic topological spaces.

Keywords: Neutrosophic set; Neutrosophic topology; Neutrosophic supra topology; Neutrosophic α -open set; Neutrosophic Φ -open set.

1. Introduction

Smarandache [53] defined the Neutrosophic Set (NS) in 1998 by extending fuzzy set [58], and intuitionistic fuzzy set [2] to deal with uncertain, inconsistent and indeterminate information. An NS Θ defined over the universe Ω , $\alpha = \alpha(\xi, \psi, \zeta) \in \Theta$ with ξ, ψ and ζ being the real standard or non-standard subsets of $]0, 1^+ [$. ξ, ψ and ζ are the degrees of true membership function, indeterminate membership function and falsity membership function respectively in the set Θ . Wang, Smarandache, Zhang, and Sunderraman [56] defined Interval NS (INS) as an instance and a subclass of NS by considering the subunitary interval $[0, 1]$. An INS τ defined on universe Ω , $\alpha = \alpha(\xi, \psi, \zeta) \in \tau$ with ξ, ψ and ζ being the subinterval of $[0, 1]$. Wang, Smarandache, Zhang, and Sunderraman [57] defined Single Valued NS (SVNS) as an instance of NS. In SVNS, the degrees of truth-membership function, indeterminacy-membership function and falsity-membership function lie in the interval $[0, 1]$. NS has drawn many researchers' much attention for theoretical as well as practical applications [3-18, 24, 26-34, 36-46, 54-55].

Salama and Alblowi [49] grounded the concept of Neutrosophic Topological Space (NTS). Salama and Alblowi [50] also studied the generalized NS and generalized NTS. Salama, Smarandache and Alblowi [51] presented a new concept on neutrosophic crisp topology. Iswaraya and Bageerathi [23] presented the neutrosophic semi-closed set and neutrosophic semi-open set. Arokiarani, Dhavaseelan, Jafari, and Parimala [1] present the neutrosophic semi-open functions and established some relations between them. Rao and Srinivasa [48] presented neutrosophic pre-open

set and pre-closed set. Dhavaseelan, Parimala, Jafari, and Smarandache [20] presented the neutrosophic semi-supra open set and neutrosophic semi-supra continuous functions.

Dhavaseelan, Ganster, Jafari, and Parimala [21] presented the neutrosophic α -supra open set and neutrosophic α -supra continuous functions. Parimala, Karthika, Dhavaseelan, & Jafari [35] presented the neutrosophic supra pre- continuous functions, the neutrosophic supra pre-open maps, and the neutrosophic supra pre-closed maps in terms of neutrosophic supra pre-open sets and neutrosophic supra pre-closed sets. Dhavaseelan, and Jafari [21] studied Generalized Neutrosophic Closed Set (GNCS). Pushpalatha and Nandhini [47] defined the GNCS in NTSs. Ebenanjar, Immaculate, and Wilfred [22] studied neutrosophic b -open sets in NTSs. Maheswari, Sathyabama, and Chandrasekar [25] studied the neutrosophic generalized b - closed sets in NTSs. Das and Pramanik [17] presented the generalized neutrosophic b -open sets in NTSs.

Research gap: No study on neutrosophic Φ -open sets and neutrosophic Φ -continuous functions neutrosophic generalized b -open set has been reported in the recent literature.

Motivation: To fill the research gap, we introduce the neutrosophic Φ -open set.

In this paper, we develop the notion of neutrosophic Φ -open set and neutrosophic Φ -continuous mapping, neutrosophic Φ -open mapping, and neutrosophic Φ -closed mapping via NTSs.

The rest of the paper is designed as follows:

Section 2 recalls the definitions neutrosophic set, neutrosophic topological space, neutrosophic supra topological space, neutrosophic α -open sets, and neutrosophic α -closed sets. Section 3 introduces neutrosophic Φ -open set, neutrosophic Φ -continuous mapping, and neutrosophic Φ -open mapping and proofs of some remarks, and theorems on neutrosophic Φ -open sets and neutrosophic Φ -continuous mapping. Section 4 presents concluding remarks.

2. Preliminaries and some properties

In this section, we discuss some existing definitions and theorems which are already defined by many researchers.

Definition 2.1. Assume that W be a universal set. Then D , an NS [53] over W is denoted as follows:
 $D = \{(m, T_D(m), I_D(m), F_D(m)) : m \in W \text{ and } T_D(m), I_D(m), F_D(m) \in]0,1^+[\}$ where T_D, I_D and F_D are the functions from D to $]0,1^+[$ and for each $y \in W, -0 \leq T_D(m)+I_D(m)+F_D(m) \leq 3^+$.

Definition 2.2. Assume that $D = \{(m, T_D(m), I_D(m), F_D(m)) : m \in W\}$ and $K = \{(m, T_K(m), I_K(m), F_K(m)) : m \in W\}$ are any two NS over W , then $D \cup K$ and $D \cap K$ [53] are defined by

- i. $D \cup K = \{(m, T_D(m) \vee T_K(m), I_D(m) \wedge I_K(m), F_D(m) \wedge F_K(m)) : m \in W\};$
- ii. $D \cap K = \{(m, T_D(m) \wedge T_K(m), I_D(m) \vee I_K(m), F_D(m) \vee F_K(m)) : m \in W\}.$

Definition 2.3. Assume that $D = \{(m, T_D(m), I_D(m), F_D(m)) : m \in W\}$ is an NS over W . Then the complement [53] of D is defined by $D^c = \{(m, 1-T_D(m), 1-I_D(m), 1-F_D(m)) : m \in W\}.$

Definition 2.4. Assume that $D = \{(m, T_D(m), I_D(m), F_D(m)): m \in W\}$ and $K = \{(m, T_K(m), I_K(m), F_K(m)): m \in W\}$ are any two NSs over W . Then D is contained in K [53] if and only if $T_D(m) \leq T_K(m)$, $I_D(m) \geq I_K(m)$, $F_D(m) \geq F_K(m)$, for all $m \in W$.

Now we may consider two NSs 0_N and 1_N over W as follows:

- 1) $0_N = \{(m, 0, 1, 1): m \in W\}$;
- 2) $1_N = \{(m, 1, 0, 0): m \in W\}$.

Clearly, $0_N \subseteq 1_N$.

Definition 2.5. Assume that W is a universe of discourse and τ is the collection of some NSs over W . Then the collection τ is said to be a Neutrosophic Topology (NT) [49] on W if the following axioms hold:

1. $0_N, 1_N \in \tau$
2. $C_1, C_2 \in \tau \Rightarrow C_1 \cap C_2 \in \tau$
3. $\cup C_i \in \tau$, for every $\{C_i: i \in \Delta\} \subseteq \tau$.

The pair (W, τ) is said to be an NTS. If $H \in \tau$, then H is called a Neutrosophic Open Set (NOS) and the complement of H i.e. H^c is called a Neutrosophic Closed Set (NCS).

Example 2.1. Assume that $W = \{s_1, s_2, s_3\}$ is a set with three NSs over W as follows:

$M_1 = \{(s_1, 0.9, 0.5, 0.7), (s_2, 0.7, 0.6, 0.8), (s_3, 0.7, 0.4, 0.7): s_1, s_2, s_3 \in W\}$;

$M_2 = \{(s_1, 1.0, 0.3, 0.4), (s_2, 0.9, 0.5, 0.5), (s_3, 1.0, 0.1, 0.5): s_1, s_2, s_3 \in W\}$;

$M_3 = \{(s_1, 0.9, 0.3, 0.5), (s_2, 0.8, 0.5, 0.8), (s_3, 0.9, 0.3, 0.5): s_1, s_2, s_3 \in W\}$;

Then (W, τ) is an NTS, where $\tau = \{0_N, 1_N, M_1, M_2, M_3\}$ is an NT on W .

Remark 2.1. The collection of all NOSs and NCSs in (W, τ) may be denoted as $NOS(W)$ and $NCS(W)$ respectively. The neutrosophic interior and neutrosophic closure [49] of a neutrosophic subset H of W is denoted by $N_{int}(H)$ and $N_{cl}(H)$ respectively and defined as follows:

$N_{int}(H) = \cup \{D: D \text{ is an NOS in } W \text{ and } D \subseteq H\}$,

$N_{cl}(H) = \cap \{L: L \text{ is an NCS in } W \text{ and } H \subseteq L\}$.

Clearly $N_{int}(H) \subseteq H \subseteq N_{cl}(H)$.

Definition 2.6. Assume that (W, τ) is an NTS and H be an NS over W . Then H is

- 1) Neutrosophic Pre-Open (NPO) set [48] iff $H \subseteq N_{int}N_{cl}(H)$;
- 2) Neutrosophic Semi-Open (NSO) set [23] iff $H \subseteq N_{cl}N_{int}(H)$;
- 3) Neutrosophic α -Open ($N\alpha$ -O) set [1] iff $H \subseteq N_{int}N_{cl}N_{int}(H)$.

Definition 2.7. Assume that W is a universal set and Ω be the collection of some NSs over W . Then Ω is said to be a Neutrosophic Supra Topology (NST) [19] on W if the following axioms hold:

- 1) $0_N, 1_N \in \Omega$
- 2) $\cup C_i \in \Omega$, for every $\{C_i: i \in \Delta\} \subseteq \Omega$.

The pair (W, Ω) is said to be a Neutrosophic Supra Topological Space (NSTS). If $H \in \Omega$, then H is called a Neutrosophic-Supra Open (N-SO) set and its complement H^c is called a Neutrosophic-Supra Closed (N-SC) set in (W, Ω) . The neutrosophic-supra interior and neutrosophic-supra closure of an NS H is denoted by $N_{int}^\Omega(H)$ and $N_{cl}^\Omega(H)$ respectively and are defined as follows:

$$N_{int}^\Omega(H) = \cup \{D : D \text{ is an N-SO set in } W \text{ and } D \subseteq H\},$$

$$N_{cl}^\Omega(H) = \cap \{L : L \text{ is an N-SC set in } W \text{ and } H \subseteq L\}.$$

Definition 2.8. Assume that (W, Ω) be an NSTS and H is an NS over W . Then H is

- 1) Neutrosophic-Pre Supra Open (N-PSO) set [35] iff $H \subseteq N_{int}^\Omega(N_{cl}^\Omega(H))$;
- 2) Neutrosophic-Semi Supra Open (N-SSO) set [20] if and only if $H \subseteq N_{cl}^\Omega(N_{int}^\Omega(H))$;
- 3) Neutrosophic- α -Supra Open (N- α SO) set [19] if and only if $H \subseteq N_{int}^\Omega(N_{cl}^\Omega(N_{int}^\Omega(H)))$.

The complement of N-PSO set, N-SSO set and N- α SO set are called Neutrosophic Pre Supra-Closed (N-PSC) set, Neutrosophic Semi Supra-Closed (N-SSC) set and Neutrosophic α -Supra-Closed (N- α SC) set respectively.

Theorem 2.1. Assume that (W, Ω) be an NSTS.

Then

- i. Every N-SO set is an N- α SO set.
- ii. Every N- α SO set is an N-PSO set (N-SSO set).

For proof, see Parimala, Karthika, Dhavaseelan, and Jafari (2018).

Theorem 2.2. Assume that (W, Ω) be an NSTS.

Then

- i. Union of two N- α SO sets is an N- α SO set.
- ii. Intersection of two N- α SO sets may not be an N- α SO set in general.

For proof, see [19].

Definition 2.9. Let (W, Ω) and (M, Π) be any two NTSs. Then a function $\xi : (W, \Omega) \rightarrow (Y, M)$ is called a neutrosophic continuous function [52] if the inverse image of each NOS G in M is an NOS in W .

Definition 2.10. Let (W, Ω) and (M, Π) be any two NSTSs. Then a function $\xi : (W, \Omega) \rightarrow (Y, M)$ is called a neutrosophic supra continuous [19] if and only if the inverse image of each N-SO set G in M is an N-SO set in W .

Definition 2.11. A function $\xi : (W, \Omega) \rightarrow (M, \Pi)$, where (W, Ω) and (M, Π) are two NSTSs is said to be a neutrosophic α -supra [19] continuous iff $\xi^{-1}(G)$ is an N- α SO set in W whenever G is an N-SO set in M .

Theorem 2.3. Assume that ξ be a function from an NSTS (W, Ω) to another NSTS (M, Π) . Then the following statements [19] are equivalent:

- i. ξ is a neutrosophic α -supra continuous mapping.
- ii. $\xi^{-1}(G)$ is an N- α SC set in W whenever G is an N-SC set in M .

3. Neutrosophic Φ -open set and neutrosophic Φ -continuous mapping

Definition 3.1. Assume that (W, τ) is an NTS and H is an NS over W . Then H is called a Neutrosophic Φ -Open (N- Φ -O) set iff there exist an N α -O set K such that $K \subseteq H \subseteq N_{cl}(K)$, where $N_{cl}(K)$ denotes the neutrosophic closure of K with respect to the NT τ on W .

Theorem 3.1. In an NTS (W, τ) ,

- 1) Every NOS is a neutrosophic Φ -open set;
- 2) Every N α -O set is a neutrosophic Φ -open set.

Proof.

- 1) Assume that Q is an NOS in an NTS (W, τ) . Since every NOS is an N α -O set, so Q is an N α -O set in (W, τ) . Clearly $Q \subseteq Q \subseteq N_{cl}(Q)$. Therefore, Q is a neutrosophic Φ -open set. Hence every NOS in (W, τ) is a neutrosophic Φ -open set.
- 2) Assume that R is an N α -O set in an NTS (W, τ) . For any neutrosophic set R , $R \subseteq R \subseteq N_{cl}(R)$. Therefore, there exists an N α -O set R in (W, τ) such that $R \subseteq R \subseteq N_{cl}(R)$. Hence R is a neutrosophic Φ -open set. Thus, every N α -O set in (W, τ) is a neutrosophic Φ -open set.

Theorem 3.2. Assume that (W, τ) is an NTS and θ is a neutrosophic supra topology such that $\tau \subseteq \theta$. Then

- 1) Every neutrosophic Φ -open set in (W, τ) is a neutrosophic Φ -supra open set in (W, θ) ;
- 2) Every NOS in (W, τ) is a neutrosophic Φ -supra open set in (W, θ) .

Proof.

- 1) Assume that (W, τ) is an NTS and θ is an NST such that $\tau \subseteq \theta$. Assume that Q is an arbitrary neutrosophic Φ -open set in (W, τ) . Then there exists an N α -O set K such that $K \subseteq Q \subseteq N_{cl}(K)$, where $N_{cl}(K)$ denotes the neutrosophic closure of K with respect to the topology τ . Since $\tau \subseteq \theta$ and θ is an NST on W , so $N_{cl}(K) \subseteq N_{cl}^\theta(K)$, where $N_{cl}^\theta(K)$ denotes the neutrosophic supra-closure of K with respect to the NST θ . Therefore $K \subseteq Q \subseteq N_{cl}^\theta(K)$.

Hence Q is a neutrosophic Φ -supra open set in (W, θ) .

- 2) Assume that (W, τ) is an NTS and θ be an NST on W such that $\tau \subseteq \theta$.

Assume that Q be an arbitrary NOS in (W, τ) . From Theorem 3.1, it is clear that every NOS in an NTS (W, τ) is a neutrosophic Φ -open set. So, Q is a neutrosophic Φ -open set in (W, τ) .

From the first part of the theorem 3.2, it is clear that Q is a neutrosophic Φ -open set in (W, θ) .

Hence every NOS in an NTS (W, τ) is a neutrosophic Φ -supra open set in the NSTS (W, θ) .

Lemma 3.1. In an NTS (W, τ) , the union of two neutrosophic Φ -open sets is a neutrosophic Φ -open set.

Proof.

Assume that K and L are any two neutrosophic Φ -open sets in an NTS (W, τ) . Then there exist two $N\alpha$ -O sets Q_1 and Q_2 in (W, τ) such that $Q_1 \subseteq K \subseteq N_{cl}(Q_1)$, $Q_2 \subseteq L \subseteq N_{cl}(Q_2)$.

Now, $Q_1 \cup Q_2 \subseteq K \cup L \subseteq N_{cl}(Q_1) \cup N_{cl}(Q_2) = N_{cl}(Q_1 \cup Q_2)$ and $Q_1 \cup Q_2$ is an $N\alpha$ -O set in (W, τ) . Therefore $K \cup L$ is a neutrosophic Φ -open set in (W, τ) . Hence the union of two neutrosophic Φ -open sets in an NTS (W, τ) is a neutrosophic Φ -open set.

Theorem 3.3. Assume that (W, τ) is an NTS. Then

- 1) Union of an NOS and a neutrosophic Φ -open set is a neutrosophic Φ -open set.
- 2) Union of an $N\alpha$ -O set and a neutrosophic Φ -open set is a neutrosophic Φ -open set.

Proof. Let Q be an NOS and R be a neutrosophic Φ -open set in an NTS (W, τ) . From Theorem 3.1, Q is a neutrosophic Φ -open set. Again, from Lemma 3.1, it is clear that $Q \cup R$ is a neutrosophic Φ -open set in (W, τ) .

- 1) Assume that H is an $N\alpha$ -O set and G is a neutrosophic Φ -open set in an NTS (W, τ) . From Theorem 3.1, it is clear that H is a neutrosophic Φ -open set. Again, from Remark 3.1, it is clear that $H \cup G$ is a neutrosophic Φ -open set in (W, τ) .

Definition 3.2. Assume that (W, τ) and (M, δ) are two NTSs. Then a function $\xi: (W, \tau) \rightarrow (M, \delta)$ is called a neutrosophic Φ -continuous function iff the inverse image of every NOS G in M is a neutrosophic Φ -open set in W .

Definition 3.3. Assume that (W, τ) , and (M, δ) are two NTSs and θ is an NST on W such that $\tau \subseteq \theta$. Then a function $\xi: (W, \tau) \rightarrow (M, \delta)$ is called a neutrosophic Φ -supra continuous function iff the inverse image of every NOS G in M is a neutrosophic Φ -supra open set in W with respect to the NST θ on W .

Theorem 3.3. Every neutrosophic continuous function from an NTS (W, τ) to another NTS (M, δ) is a neutrosophic Φ -continuous function.

Proof. Assume that $\xi: (W, \tau) \rightarrow (M, \delta)$ is a neutrosophic continuous function and K be an arbitrary NOS in M . Then by hypothesis, $\xi^{-1}(K)$ is an NOS in W . Since each NOS is a neutrosophic Φ -open set, so $\xi^{-1}(K)$ is a neutrosophic Φ -open set in W . Therefore, for each NOS K in M , $\xi^{-1}(K)$ is a neutrosophic Φ -open set in W . Hence ξ is a neutrosophic Φ -continuous function. Therefore, every neutrosophic continuous function is a neutrosophic Φ -continuous function.

Theorem 3.4. Assume that (W, τ) and (M, δ) are two NTSs and $\tau \subseteq \theta$, where θ is an NST on W . Then every neutrosophic Φ -continuous function from (W, τ) to (M, δ) is a neutrosophic Φ -supra continuous function from (W, θ) to (M, δ) .

Proof. Assume that $\xi: (W, \tau) \rightarrow (M, \delta)$ is a neutrosophic Φ -continuous mapping. Let θ be an NST such that $\tau \subseteq \theta$. Let T be an NOS in M . Then by hypothesis $\xi^{-1}(T)$ is a neutrosophic Φ -open set in W . Since each neutrosophic Φ -open set (W, τ) is a neutrosophic Φ -supra open set in (W, θ) , so $\xi^{-1}(T)$ is a neutrosophic Φ -supra open set in (W, θ) . Therefore ξ is a neutrosophic Φ -supra continuous mapping from (W, θ) to (M, δ) .

Definition 3.4. Let (W, τ) and (M, δ) be two NTSs. A function $\xi: (W, \tau) \rightarrow (M, \delta)$ is called a neutrosophic Φ -open function if $\xi(Q)$ is a neutrosophic Φ -open set in M for each NOS Q in W .

Definition 3.5. Let (W, τ) and (M, δ) be two NTSs. A function $\xi: (W, \tau) \rightarrow (M, \delta)$ is called a neutrosophic Φ -closed function if $\xi(Q)$ is a neutrosophic Φ -closed set in M for each NCS Q in W .

Theorem 3.5. Assume that (W, τ) and (M, δ) are any two NTSs. Then $\xi: (W, \tau) \rightarrow (M, \delta)$ is a neutrosophic Φ -open function iff $\xi(N_{int}(K)) \subseteq N_{int}(\xi(K))$, for each neutrosophic subset K of W .

Proof. Let $\xi: (W, \tau) \rightarrow (M, \delta)$ be a neutrosophic Φ -open function and K be a neutrosophic subset of W . Clearly $N_{int}(K)$ is an NOS in W and $N_{int}(K) \subseteq K$. Since ξ is a neutrosophic Φ -open function, so $\xi(N_{int}(K))$ is a neutrosophic Φ -open set in M and $\xi(N_{int}(K)) \subseteq \xi(K)$. Since each NOS is a neutrosophic Φ -open set and $N_{int}(\xi(K))$ is the largest NOS contained in $\xi(K)$, so $N_{int}(\xi(K))$ is the largest neutrosophic Φ -open set contained in $\xi(K)$. Therefore $\xi(N_{int}(K)) \subseteq N_{int}(\xi(K)) \subseteq \xi(K)$ i.e. $\xi(N_{int}(K)) \subseteq N_{int}(\xi(K))$. Hence for each neutrosophic subset K of W , $\xi(N_{int}(K)) \subseteq N_{int}(\xi(K))$.

Conversely, let L be an NOS in (W, τ) . Therefore, $N_{int}(L) = L$. Now by hypothesis $\xi(N_{int}(L)) \subseteq N_{int}(\xi(L))$. This implies $\xi(L) \subseteq N_{int}(\xi(L))$. We know that $N_{int}(\xi(L)) \subseteq \xi(L)$. Therefore $\xi(L) = N_{int}(\xi(L))$. This means that $\xi(L)$ is an NOS in (M, δ) . Since each NOS is a neutrosophic Φ -open set, so $\xi(L)$ is a neutrosophic Φ -open set in (M, δ) . Hence for each NOS L in (W, τ) , $\xi(L)$ is a neutrosophic Φ -open set in (M, δ) . Therefore ξ is a neutrosophic Φ -open function.

Theorem 3.6. Assume that ξ is a bijective function from an NTS (W, τ) to another NTS (M, δ) . Then the following mathematical statements are equivalent:

- 1) ξ is a neutrosophic Φ -continuous function;
- 2) ξ is a neutrosophic Φ -closed function;
- 3) ξ is a neutrosophic Φ -open function.

Proof.

(1) \Rightarrow (2) Assume that $\xi: (W, \tau) \rightarrow (M, \delta)$ is a neutrosophic Φ -continuous function. Let Q be any arbitrary NCS in (W, τ) . Then Q^c is an NOS in (W, τ) . Since each NOS is a neutrosophic Φ -open set, so Q^c is a neutrosophic Φ -open set in (W, τ) . Since ξ is a bijective function, so $\xi(Q^c) = (\xi(Q))^c$ is an NOS in (M, δ) . Hence $\xi(Q)$ is an NCS in (M, δ) . Therefore, for each NCS Q in (W, τ) , $\xi(Q)$ is a neutrosophic Φ -closed set in (M, δ) . Hence ξ is a neutrosophic Φ -closed function.

(2) \Rightarrow (3) Assume that $\xi: (W, \tau) \rightarrow (M, \delta)$ be a neutrosophic Φ -closed function. Let L be any arbitrary NOS in (W, τ) . Then L^c is an NCS in (W, τ) . Since ξ is a neutrosophic Φ -closed function, so $\xi(L^c) = (\xi(L))^c$ is a neutrosophic Φ -closed set in (M, δ) . Then $\xi(L)$ is a neutrosophic Φ -open set in (M, δ) . Therefore, for each NOS L in (W, τ) , $\xi(L)$ is a neutrosophic Φ -open set in (M, δ) . Hence ξ is a neutrosophic Φ -open function.

(3) \Rightarrow (1) Assume that $\xi: (W, \tau) \rightarrow (M, \delta)$ is a neutrosophic Φ -open function. Let P be any arbitrary NOS in (M, δ) . Then P is a neutrosophic Φ -open set in (M, δ) . Since ξ is a bijective function, so $\xi^{-1}(P)$ is an NOS in (W, τ) . Again, since each NOS is a neutrosophic Φ -open set, so $\xi^{-1}(P)$ is a neutrosophic Φ -open set in (W, τ) . Therefore, for each NOS P in (M, δ) , $\xi^{-1}(P)$ is a neutrosophic Φ -open set in (W, τ) . Hence ξ is a neutrosophic Φ -continuous function.

4. Conclusion

In this study we have introduced neutrosophic Φ -open set, neutrosophic Φ -continuous mapping via NTSs and investigated their several properties. By defining neutrosophic Φ -open set, neutrosophic Φ -continuous mapping, we have proved some remarks, and theorems on NTSs. In the future, we hope that based on Φ -open set, neutrosophic Φ -continuous mapping via NTSs, many new investigations can be carried out.

References

1. Arokiarani, I., Dhavaseelan, R., Jafari, S., & Parimala, M. (2017). On some new notations and functions in neutrosophic topological spaces. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 16,16-19.
2. Atanassov, K. T. (1986). Intuitionistic fuzzy sets. *Fuzzy Sets and Systems*, 20(1), 87-96.
3. Biswas, P, Pramanik, S. & Giri, B.C. (2014). Entropy based grey relational analysis method for multi-attribute decision making under single valued neutrosophic assessments. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 2, 102-110.
4. Biswas, P, Pramanik, S. & Giri, B.C. (2014). A new methodology for neutrosophic multi-attribute decision-making with unknown weight information. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 3, 42-50.
5. Biswas, P., Pramanik, S., & Giri, B. C. (2014). Cosine similarity measure based multi-attribute decision-making with trapezoidal fuzzy neutrosophic numbers. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 8, 46-56.
6. Biswas, P, Pramanik, S. & Giri, B. C. (2016). Aggregation of triangular fuzzy neutrosophic set information and its application to multi-attribute decision making. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 12, 20-40.
7. Biswas, P, Pramanik, S. & Giri, B. C. (2016). Value and ambiguity index based ranking method of single-valued trapezoidal neutrosophic numbers and its application to multi-attribute decision making. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 12, 127-138.
8. Biswas, P, Pramanik, S. & Giri, B. C. (2016). TOPSIS method for multi-attribute group decision making under single-valued neutrosophic environment. *Neural Computing and Applications*, 27(3), 727-737.
9. Biswas, P., Pramanik, S., & Giri, B. C. (2018). Distance measure based MADM strategy with interval trapezoidal neutrosophic numbers. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 19, 40-46.
10. Biswas, P., Pramanik, S., & Giri, B. C. (2018). TOPSIS strategy for multi-attribute decision making with trapezoidal neutrosophic numbers. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*,19, 29-39.
11. Biswas, P., Pramanik, S., & Giri, B. C. (2018). Multi-attribute group decision making based on expected value of neutrosophic trapezoidal numbers. In F. Smarandache, & S. Pramanik (Eds., vol.2), *New trends in neutrosophic theory and applications* (pp. 103-124). Brussels: Pons Editions.
12. Biswas, P., Pramanik, S., & Giri, B. C. (2019). NH-MADM strategy in neutrosophic hesitant fuzzy set environment based on extended GRA. *Informatica*, 30 (2), 1–30.
13. Biswas, P., Pramanik, S., & Giri, B. C. (2019). Non-linear programming approach for single-valued neutrosophic TOPSIS method. *New Mathematics and Natural Computation*, 15 (2), 307-326.

14. Biswas, P., Pramanik, S., & Giri, B. C. (2019). Neutrosophic TOPSIS with group decision making. In C. Kahraman & I. Otaç (Eds.), *Fuzzy multicriteria decision making using neutrosophic sets, studies in fuzziness and soft computing* 369. doi: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-00045-5_21.
15. Broumi, S., Bakali, A., Talea, M., Smarandache, F., Uluçay, V., Sahin, S., & Pramanik, S. (2018). Neutrosophic sets: An overview. In F. Smarandache, & S. Pramanik (Eds., vol.2), *New trends in neutrosophic theory and applications* (pp. 403-434). Brussels: Pons Editions.
16. Das, S., Roy, B. K., Kar, M. B., Kar, S., & Pamučar, D. (2020). Neutrosophic fuzzy set and its application in decision making. *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing*. doi:10.1007/s12652-020-01808-3
17. Das, S., & Pramanik, S. (2020). Generalized neutrosophic b-open sets in neutrosophic topological space. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 35, 522-530.
18. Das, S., & Pramanik, S. (2020). Neutrosophic simply soft open set in neutrosophic soft topological space. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*. In Press.
19. Dhavaseelan, R., Ganster, M., Jafari, S., & Parimala, M. (2018). On neutrosophic α -supra open sets and neutrosophic α -supra continuous functions. In F. Smarandache, & S. Pramanik (Eds., vol.2), *New trends in neutrosophic theory and applications* (pp. 289-297). Brussels: Pons Editions.
20. Dhavaseelan, R., Parimala, M., Jafari, S., & Smarandache, F. (2017). On neutrosophic semi-supra open set and neutrosophic semi-supra continuous functions. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 16, 39-43.
21. Dhavaseelan, R., & Jafari, S. (2018). Generalized neutrosophic closed sets. In F. Smarandache, & S. Pramanik (Eds., vol.2), *New trends in neutrosophic theory and applications* (pp. 261-273). Brussels: Pons Editions.
22. Ebenanjar, E., Immaculate, J., & Wilfred, C. B. (2018). On neutrosophic b -open sets in neutrosophic topological space. *Journal of Physics Conference Series*, 1139(1), 012062. doi: 10.1088/1742-6596/1139/1/012062
23. Iswarya, P., & Bageerathi, K. (2016). On neutrosophic semi-open sets in neutrosophic topological spaces. *International Journal of Mathematical Trends and Technology*, 37(3), 214-223.
24. Khalid, H. E. (2020). Neutrosophic geometric programming (NGP) with (max-product) operator, an innovative model. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 32, 269-281.
25. Maheswari, C., Sathyabama, M., & Chandrasekar, S. (2018). Neutrosophic generalized b-closed sets in neutrosophic topological spaces. *Journal of Physics Conference Series*, 1139(1), 012065. doi: 10.1088/1742-6596/1139/1/012065

26. Mallick, R., & Pramanik, S. (2020). Pentapartitioned neutrosophic set and its properties. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 36, 184-192.
27. Mondal, K., & Pramanik, S. (2015). Neutrosophic decision making model of school choice. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 7, 62-68.
28. Mondal, K., & Pramanik, S. (2015). Neutrosophic tangent similarity measure and its application to multiple attribute decision making. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 9, 80-87.
29. Mondal, K., & Pramanik, S. (2015). Neutrosophic decision making model for clay-brick selection in construction field based on grey relational analysis. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 9, 64-71.
30. Mondal, K., Pramanik, S., & Giri, B. C. (2018). Single valued neutrosophic hyperbolic sine similarity measure based MADM strategy. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 20, 3-11.
31. Mondal, K., Pramanik, S., & Giri, B. C. (2018). Hybrid binary logarithm similarity measure for MAGDM problems under SVNS assessments. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 20, 12-25.
32. Mondal, K., Pramanik, S. & Smarandache, F. (2016). Rough neutrosophic TOPSIS for multi-attribute group decision making. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 13, 105-117.
33. Mondal, K., Pramanik, S. & Smarandache, F. (2016). Multi-attribute decision making based on rough neutrosophic variational coefficient similarity measure. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 13, 3-17.
34. Nguyen, G.N., Son, L.H., Ashour, A.S., & Dey, N. (2019). A survey of the state-of-the-arts on neutrosophic sets in biomedical diagnoses. *International Journal of Machine Learning and Cybernetics*, 10, 1-13.
35. Parimala, M., Karthika, M., Dhavaseelan, R., & Jafari, S. (2018). On neutrosophic supra p -continuous functions in neutrosophic topological spaces. In F. Smarandache, & S. Pramanik (Eds., vol.2), *New trends in neutrosophic theory and applications* (pp. 356-368).
36. Peng, X., & Dai, J. (2020). A bibliometric analysis of neutrosophic set: Two decades review from 1998 to 2017. *Artificial Intelligence Review*, 53(1), 199-255.
37. Pramanik, S. (2013). A critical review of Vivekanada's educational thoughts for women education based on neutrosophic logic. *MS Academic*, 3(1), 191-198.
38. Pramanik, S. (2020). Rough neutrosophic set: an overview. In F. Smarandache, & Broumi, S. (Eds.), *Neutrosophic theories in communication, management and information technology* (pp.275-311). New York. Nova Science Publishers.
39. Pramanik, S., Biswas, P., & Giri, B. C. (2017). Hybrid vector similarity measures and their applications to multi-attribute decision making under neutrosophic environment. *Neural Computing and Applications*, 28 (5), 1163-1176.

40. Pramanik, S., & Chackrabarti, S.N. (2013). A study on problems of construction workers in West Bengal based on neutrosophic cognitive maps. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology*, 2(11), 6387-6394.
41. Pramanik, S., Dey, P.P., & Smarandache, F. (2018). Correlation coefficient measures of interval bipolar neutrosophic sets for solving multi-attribute decision making problems. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 19,70-79.
42. Pramanik, S., & Mallick, R. (2018). VIKOR based MAGDM strategy with trapezoidal neutrosophic numbers. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 22, 118-130.
43. Pramanik, S., and Mallick, R. (2019). TODIM strategy for multi-attribute group decision making in trapezoidal neutrosophic number environment. *Complex & Intelligent Systems*, 5 (4), 379–389.
44. Pramanik, S., & Mallick, R. (2020). MULTIMOORA strategy for solving multi-attribute group decision making (MAGDM) in trapezoidal neutrosophic number environment. *CAAI Transactions on Intelligence Technology*, 5(3), 150-156.
45. Pramanik, S., & Mondal, K. (2015). Interval neutrosophic multi-attribute decision-making based on grey relational analysis. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 9, 13-22.
46. Pramanik, S., & Roy, T.K. (2014). Neutrosophic game theoretic approach to Indo-Pak conflict over Jammu-Kashmir. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 2, 82-101.
47. Pushpalatha, A., & Nandhini, T. (2019). Generalized closed sets via neutrosophic topological spaces. *Malaya Journal of Matematik*, 7(1), 50-54.
48. Rao, V. V., & Srinivasa, R. (2017). Neutrosophic pre-open sets and pre-closed sets in neutrosophic topology. *International Journal of Chem Tech Research*, 10(10), 449-458.
49. Salama, A. A., & Alblowi, S. A. (2012). Neutrosophic set and neutrosophic topological space. *ISOR Journal of Mathematics*, 3(4), 31-35.
50. Salama, A. A., & Alblowi, S. A. (2012). Generalized neutrosophic set and generalized neutrosophic topological space. *Computer Science and Engineering*, 2 (7), 129-132.
51. Salama, A. A., Smarandache, F., & Alblowi, S. A. (2014). New neutrosophic crisp topological concepts. *Neutrosophic Sets and System*, 4, 50-54.
52. Salama, A. A., Smarandache, F., & Kromov, V. (2014). Neutrosophic closed set and neutrosophic continuous functions. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 4, 4-8.
53. Smarandache, F. (1998). *A unifying field in logics, neutrosophy: neutrosophic probability, set and logic*. Rehoboth: American Research Press.
54. Smarandache, F. & Pramanik, S. (Eds.). (2016). *New trends in neutrosophic theory and applications*. Brussels: Pons Editions.
55. Smarandache, F. & Pramanik, S. (Eds.). (2018). *New trends in neutrosophic theory and applications, Vol.2*. Brussels: Pons Editions.

56. Wang, H., Smarandache, F., Zhang, Y.Q., & Sunderraman, R. (2005). Interval neutrosophic sets and logic: theory and applications in computing. Arizona, Hexis.
57. Wang, H., Smarandache F., Zhang, Y.Q., & Sunderraman, R. (2010). Single valued neutrosophic sets. *Multispace and Multistructure*, 4, 410-413.
58. Zadeh, L. A. (1965). Fuzzy sets. *Information and Control*, 8(3), 338-353.

Received: June 7, 2020. Accepted: Nov 30, 2020